

THE CONCEPT OF EXISTENCE AND ITS MAIN TYPES

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Abstract.

Any issue that philosophy studies, we will see that it is related to the problem of existence. The problem of existence is the basis of any worldview and methodological problems in philosophy.

Key words: ontology, matter, space, neutron, electron, positron, atom, molecule.

Philosophers who argued about the existence of the world, that is, their existence, approached this issue in different ways: their arguments say that the world existed before, exists now, and will exist in the future; others, the world did not exist before, the first being is God, the creator of all things and events in this world. The first being, that is, the first being, God, is said to be the first cause of the existence of all beings.

"The First One, (God)," says Farabi, is different from all other things by its original nature" (Abu Nasr Farabi "The City of Virtuous People", p. 131). Because it is not a substance, it is not a subject, it does not have a form, it is unique in this existence, it is the first in this respect. "Hegel interpreted ontology as 'the doctrine of the abstract definition of the essence of absolute spirit'"¹

As a result of the development of science and practice, the previous views about the creation of the world, its limitation and limitation in space and time were gradually replaced by views about its unlimitedness, at the same time, its unity, permanence, and eternity.

All things in the eternal world, various inanimate and animate organisms, people and their activities, even the whole society, are undoubtedly temporary. Therefore, existence is eternal, but everything in it is changing and developing; in the transition from one state to another, from one type to another, because they do not exist from existence, and cannot exist from nothing.

¹ Encyclopedic Dictionary of Philosophy "Publication of the National Society of Philosophers of Uzbekistan T-2004 p. 317.

The concept of existence as a philosophical category is unique to abstract thinking, a high level of cognition, and in the process of thinking, people through this concept do not think about individual things in the world, their concrete signs and properties, but the most general aspect between all things in the world, events, processes. they think about their reality. With the help of the concept of existence, people get a scientific and philosophical idea about the objective existence of the world, its infinity, eternity and integrity.

The main forms of existence are natural existence or nature existence, human existence, spiritual existence.

Natural existence consists of the following two related but distinct aspects:

1. The original natural existence of things and events, bodies and processes in nature;
2. The natural existence of things created by man based on things and phenomena in nature.

The first appearance of natural existence is nature, which includes things and phenomena, processes and situations that exist independently of man and his consciousness. This is also called "primary nature" in some literature. This "primordial nature" is eternal in space, infinite time, it is always present everywhere. Based on the materials of this "primary nature", man creates "secondary" nature with his practical activity and consciousness. Objects and phenomena of "secondary nature" are created due to the need to satisfy human needs in social life, to perform some function in social life.

The existence of "primary" and "secondary" natures is interrelated, on the one hand, they have commonalities, similarities, and unity with each other, and on the other hand, they also have certain differences in relation to each other.

"Primary nature" is infinite in space, eternal and constant in time, while "secondary nature" exists in connection with the existence of man, with his activity and consciousness, with the whole society, it has a beginning and a trial in space and time.

"Primary nature" is an endless, infinite world (universe) in which a person lives and learns; "Secondary nature" is the world of things, phenomena, and processes created by man based on learning the laws of nature.

"Secondary nature" on the one hand, like "primary nature", is an objective, real entity that exists outside of human consciousness, on the other hand, it also depends on a person, because in it people's goals, ideas, knowledge and their work

will be embodied. "Secondary nature", "primary nature" and the existence of personality (human), is the existence on their border, as a specific form of natural existence, both in relation to the existence of "primary nature" and human existence. is a relatively independent entity.

One of the unique forms of existence is human existence. In the human being, first of all, as a product of the natural development of a person, together with aspects related to both forms of natural existence, as a product of socio-historical development, a sum of aspects characteristic of all forms of social and spiritual existence is embodied in it.

"Human existence is unique in that it exists in the forms of the existence of an individual person and the existence of all humanity"².

Human existence is the only source of the development of society. Social existence includes all types of phenomena. Society is an economic, social, political, socio-ethnic, family, etc. It is a living organism that is made up of relationships and is constantly developing. Society is a necessary consequence of the development of nature.

Existence is manifested not only in a material form, but also in a spiritual and spiritual form. Spiritual existence includes various cultural and artistic works created by man, language, scientific discoveries, ideas, moral rules, philosophical, aesthetic, artistic, political, contemplative culture, spiritual experiences, religious ideas, concepts, etc. includes a set.

People's inner state, experiences, feelings, mental and spiritual world, thoughts, goals and interests, and moods are **manifestations of spiritual existence**. **Spirituality** is the source of development of society, individual and nation. It should be noted separately that thanks to independence, a wide way has been opened to study the rich history, scientific, cultural and religious heritage of the Uzbek people, and to use it as a common and priceless property of the people. As I. A. Karimov said, "Spirituality is the strength of a person, nation, society, and state." Where there is no happiness there will never be." Therefore, strengthening and developing the spiritual spirit of the people is considered the most important task of the state and society in Uzbekistan. These forms of existence (existence of things, human existence, social existence, spiritual existence) are a separate view of the whole

² Э. Юсупов Фалсафа “Шарқ нашриёт матбаа концерни Тошкент-1999 р. 171

world. Existence shows the connection and commonality between these separate forms. The general connection of existence is shown by the existence of separate things.

The search for the general essence underlying the material world causes the development of ideas about matter in philosophy.

Matter in general is a concept, abstract, a product of thought, because "matter in general" is not found in the universe, but concrete forms of matter are found. Thus, the concept that philosophers use to express the properties of all material objects in a general way is "matter". The common feature of all things and phenomena in the universe is that they exist independently, outside of our consciousness. This general characteristic of all things is reflected in the concept of private matter. So, the philosophical content of the concept of matter:

- a) that things exist independently of our consciousness and will;
- b) means that they are the source of our senses and knowledge.

The philosophical concept of matter includes not only the objects known to science at the present time, but also the things that will be discovered in the future. Matter is eternal, boundless, infinite, never disappears. The eternity of matter means that it has not been created by anyone, and that it exists, and new aspects of it are revealed thanks to each new discovery. The natural-scientific meaning of the concept of matter means its structure, variety of inexhaustible properties, and they are studied by separate sciences of nature - physics, chemistry, biology, etc.

Matter exists in two forms: substance and field. Matter in the form of substance has the form of mass, and protons, neutrons, electrons and positrons, as well as atoms and molecules composed of them, can be included in their complex. Based on the information provided by modern science, microscopic bodies consisting of molecules can be in various states: liquid, solid, gaseous, plasma, epiplasm, physical vacuum. The field appearance of matter differs from the appearance of matter in that it has mass in motion and moves at a speed close to the speed of light. Electromagnetic field, nuclear field, gravitational field - these are the field manifestations of matter. Through experiments, it is possible to see the transformation of the appearance of matter and field into one another. Therefore, the transformation of the matter and field view of matter into each other shows that the particles are composed of particles and antiparticles.

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2. Э. Юсупов Фалсафа “Шарқ нашриёт матбаа концерни Тошкент-1999 p. 171

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